

Supereulerian Locally Semicomplete Multipartite Digraphs

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Abstract: A digraph D is *eulerian* if D is strongly connected and for every vertex $v \in V(D)$, $d^+(v) = d^-(v)$. Bang-Jensen and Thomassé gave the conjecture for a digraph D that if $\lambda(D) \geq \alpha(D)$, then D is supereulerian. Bang-Jensen and Maddaloni [Journal of Graph Theory, 79(2015)8-20] proved that this conjecture holds for every semicomplete multipartite digraph. In this paper, we generalized the above known results and show that this conjecture holds for every strong locally semicomplete multipartite digraph.

Key Words: Digraph, supereulerian digraph, semicomplete digraph, locally semicomplete multipartite digraph.

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§1. Introduction

A graph G is *eulerian* if G is connected without vertices of odd degree, and G is supereulerian if G has a spanning eulerian subgraph. The purpose of this paper is to investigate the digraph version of the supereulerian problem. Given a digraph D , its underling graph, denoted by \overline{D} , is gotten from D by overlooking the directions. Let $A(D)$ and $V(D)$ be the set of arcs and vertices in D , respectively. A *walk* in D is an alternating sequence $W = x_1e_1x_2e_2 \dots x_{k-1}e_{k-1}x_k$ of vertices x_i and arcs e_j from D such that $e_i = (x_i, x_{i+1}) \in A(D)$ for $i = 1, \dots, k-1$. A walk is *closed* if $x_1 = x_k$. If all the arcs of a closed walk are distinct, we call it a *closed trail* (also called a *cycle*). If all the vertices of a walk W are distinct, we call it an (x_1, x_k) -*dipath*. A digraph $D = (V(D), A(D))$ is *strongly connected* if there is a (u, v) -dipath for any two vertices u and v . A digraph D is *weakly connected* if \overline{D} is connected. Furthermore, D is said to be *eulerian* if D is strongly connected and for every vertex $v \in V(D)$, $d^+(v) = d^-(v)$. Equivalently, D is eulerian if and only if D itself is a spanning closed trail. A digraph D is *supereulerian* if D has a spanning eulerian subdigraph. If X and Y are disjoint subsets of $V(D)$, let $A(X, Y) := \{(x, y) \in A(D) : x \in X, y \in Y\}$ (sometime, $A(X, Y)$ is simply written as (X, Y)) and $d(X, Y) := |(X, Y)|$. A *circuit* C of a digraph D is a connected subdigraph of D such that

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$d_C^+(v) = d_C^-(v) = 1$ for each vertex $v \in C$. Let $[n] = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$.

A *semicomplete digraph* is a digraph without nonadjacent vertices. A *locally semicomplete digraph* [3] is a digraph D that satisfies the following conditions: for every vertex x of D , the set $N^+(x)$ of vertices dominated by x (respectively, the set $N^-(x)$ of vertices that dominate x) induces a semicomplete digraph. Hence a semicomplete digraph is also locally semicomplete. If each vertex in a semicomplete digraph is blown up, then we get a semicomplete multipartite digraph. A digraph $D = (V, A)$ is *semicomplete multipartite* if there is a partition V_1, V_2, \dots, V_c of V into independent sets so that every vertex in V_i shares an arc with every vertex in V_j for $1 \leq i < j \leq c$.

Similarly, a *locally semicomplete multipartite digraph* D is obtained from a locally semicomplete digraph F with $V(F) = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_c\}$ by blowing up each vertex $v_i \in V(F)$ into one independent set V_i in D , such that $N_D^\lambda(x) = V_{i_1} \cup \dots \cup V_{i_p}$ for any $x \in V_i$ if and only if $N_F^\lambda(v_i) = \{v_{i_1}, \dots, v_{i_p}\}$, where $\lambda \in \{+, -\}$ and $\{v_{i_1}, \dots, v_{i_p}\} \subseteq V(F)$. If a digraph $D = (V, A)$ is locally semicomplete multipartite, then there is a partition V_1, V_2, \dots, V_c of V satisfying the following two conditions:

- (1) each V_i , called a partite set, for $i \in [c]$ is an independent set;
- (2) the set of vertices dominated by x (respectively, the set of vertices that dominate x) induces a semicomplete multipartite digraph for any vertex $x \in V$.

It can be seen that a semicomplete multipartite digraph is locally semicomplete multipartite but the inverse is not right.

Let $\kappa(D)$ and $\lambda(D)$ be the vertex-strong connectivity and the arc-strong connectivity of a digraph D , respectively. While $\alpha(D)$ and $\alpha'(D)$ denote the independence number and the matching number of D respectively, which equal to the independence number and the matching number of a graph \overline{D} , respectively.

An eulerian factor of D is a collection of arc-disjoint cycles spanning $V(D)$. There are much results about the graph to be supereulerian, for examples to see the surveys [7],[8],[12]. Contrary to the supereulerian properties of graphs, not much work has been done yet for supereulerian digraphs. Gutin [8] discussed supereulerian digraphs by using the connected (g, f) -factors; Hong et al. [10] and J. Bang-Jensen et al. [4] gave the degree sum conditions for a graph being supereulerian; Bang-Jensen and Thomassé gave the following conjecture in 2011, Bang-Jensen and Maddaloni [4] said the conjecture is unpublished.

Conjecture 1.1 *Let D be a digraph. If $\lambda(D) \geq \alpha(D)$, then D is supereulerian.*

Then by using the Hoffman's circulation theorem, the first author and Maddaloni [4] proved that for a digraph D if $\lambda(D) \geq \alpha(D)$, then D has an eulerian factor and the Conjecture 1.1 hold for all semicomplete multipartite digraphs. Algefari and Lai [2] proved that if $\lambda(D) \geq \alpha'(D) > 0$, then D has a spanning eulerian subdigraph. These two authors, Alsatami and Liu [1] gave the sufficient condition of symmetric digraphs to be supereulerian, and got the result that partially symmetric digraphs are supereulerian.

In this paper, we prove the Conjecture 1.1 for strong locally semicomplete multipartite digraphs.

§2. Locally Semicomplete Multipartite Digraphs

Lemma 2.1([4]) *Let D be a digraph. If $\lambda(D) \geq \alpha(D)$, then D has an Eulerian factor.*

From the definition of a locally semicomplete multipartite digraph, one has the following Lemma 2.2.

Lemma 2.2 *Let D be a locally semicomplete multipartite digraph. Let $x \in V(D)$ and v_1, v_2 be two distinct vertices in $N_D^+(x)$ (or $N_D^-(x)$), then each of the following results holds.*

(1) *either v_1 and v_2 belong to the same partite set in which there exists no arc between v_1 and v_2 or there exists at least an arc between v_1 and v_2 ;*

(2) *If v_1 and v_2 belong to the same partite set, then $N_D^-(v_1) = N_D^-(v_2)$ and $N_D^+(v_1) = N_D^+(v_2)$.*

Applying the similar method used in [4] we can prove the following Lemma 2.3.

Lemma 2.3 *Let D be a locally semicomplete multipartite digraph. Let \mathcal{E}_1 and \mathcal{E}_2 be two vertex disjoint closed trails. If $A(\mathcal{E}_1, \mathcal{E}_2) \neq \emptyset$ and $A(\mathcal{E}_2, \mathcal{E}_1) \neq \emptyset$, then there exists a closed trail \mathcal{E} of D such that $V(\mathcal{E}) = V(\mathcal{E}_1) \cup V(\mathcal{E}_2)$.*

Proof Consider the bipartite digraph B with partitions $V(\mathcal{E}_1), V(\mathcal{E}_2)$ and arcs $A(\mathcal{E}_1, \mathcal{E}_2) \cup A(\mathcal{E}_2, \mathcal{E}_1)$. We have two distinct cases.

Case 1. Every vertex of B has positive in- and out- degree. Then, clearly, B contains a closed trail \mathcal{E} that connects \mathcal{E}_1 and \mathcal{E}_2 , so $\mathcal{E} \cup \mathcal{E}_1 \cup \mathcal{E}_2$ is the desired trail.

Case 2. There exists one vertex of B which has no positive in-degree or out-degree.

Let $v_1 v_2 \dots v_h v_1$ be a spanning trail of \mathcal{E}_1 and let $w_1 w_2 \dots w_k w_1$ be a spanning trail of \mathcal{E}_2 . Without loss of generality, assume that there is a vertex, say x , of \mathcal{E}_1 such that x has no out-neighbors in \mathcal{E}_2 . As $A(\mathcal{E}_1, \mathcal{E}_2) \neq \emptyset$, there exists another vertex, say v_s of \mathcal{E}_1 with at least one out-neighbor in \mathcal{E}_2 . Assume $(v_s, w_t) \in A(\mathcal{E}_1, \mathcal{E}_2)$.

Now consider the out neighbors v_{s+1} and w_t of v_s . If v_{s+1} and w_t are in the same partite set V_i . By Lemma 2.2(2), $(w_{t-1}, v_{s+1}) \in A(\mathcal{E}_2, \mathcal{E}_1)$, thus, $\mathcal{E}_1 \cup \mathcal{E}_2 \cup \{(w_{t-1}, v_{s+1}), (v_s, w_t)\} \setminus \{(w_{t-1}, w_t), (v_s, v_{s+1})\}$ is the desired trail. Otherwise, by Lemma 2.2(1), there exists an arc between w_t and v_{s+1} . If $(w_t, v_{s+1}) \in A(\mathcal{E}_2, \mathcal{E}_1)$, then $\mathcal{E}_1 \cup \mathcal{E}_2 \cup \{(w_t, v_{s+1}), (v_s, w_t)\} \setminus \{(v_s, v_{s+1})\}$ is the desired trail. If $(w_t, v_{s+1}) \notin A(\mathcal{E}_2, \mathcal{E}_1)$, then $(v_{s+1}, w_t) \in A(\mathcal{E}_2, \mathcal{E}_1)$.

Next we consider two out neighbors v_{s+2} and w_t of v_{s+1} , by the similar discussion as considering v_{s+1} and w_t , one has that either D contains a closed trail \mathcal{E} such that $V(\mathcal{E}) = V(\mathcal{E}_1) \cup V(\mathcal{E}_2)$ or there exists an arc $(v_{s+2}, w_t) \in A(\mathcal{E}_2, \mathcal{E}_1)$. If the former holds, the theorem is proved. Otherwise, $(v_{s+2}, w_t) \in A(\mathcal{E}_2, \mathcal{E}_1)$.

Repeatedly using this procedures, one of the following two results holds: there exists a closed trail \mathcal{E} of D such that $V(\mathcal{E}) = V(\mathcal{E}_1) \cup V(\mathcal{E}_2)$ or every vertex in $V(\mathcal{E}_1)$ has the out neighbor w_t . Since x has no out-neighbors in \mathcal{E}_2 , the result that every vertex in $V(\mathcal{E}_1)$ has the out neighbor w_t can not happen, thus, there exists a closed trail \mathcal{E} of D such that $V(\mathcal{E}) = V(\mathcal{E}_1) \cup V(\mathcal{E}_2)$. \square

By the proof of Lemma 2.3, one has the following Lemma 2.4.

Lemma 2.4 *Let D be a locally semicomplete multipartite digraph and $\mathcal{E}_1, \mathcal{E}_2$ be two vertex disjoint closed trails. Let $(x, y) \in A(\mathcal{E}_1, \mathcal{E}_2)$ and $A(\mathcal{E}_2, \mathcal{E}_1) = \emptyset$, then $(v, y) \in A(\mathcal{E}_1, \mathcal{E}_2)$ for each $v \in V(\mathcal{E}_1)$.*

Theorem 2.5 *Let D be a locally semicomplete multipartite digraph. Then D is supereulerian if and only if it is strong and has an eulerian factor.*

Proof If D is supereulerian, equivalently, there is a spanning eulerian subdigraph in D , then clearly it is strong and has an eulerian factor which consists of the union of arc disjoint cycles spanning $V(D)$.

Now assume that D is strong and has an eulerian factor \mathcal{C} , we will show that D has a spanning eulerian subdigraph. The following is a procedure to produce a spanning eulerian subdigraph of D for a given eulerian factor.

Form a minimal collection of vertex disjoint closed trails by merging those trails of \mathcal{C} having common vertices. For any two closed trails \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{F} in the collection with $A(\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{F}) \neq \emptyset$ and $A(\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{E}) \neq \emptyset$, join \mathcal{E} and \mathcal{F} into a closed trail as in Lemma 2.3.

Let $\mathcal{E}_1, \mathcal{E}_2, \dots, \mathcal{E}_t$ be the collection of closed trails of D obtained after the first step is no more applicable. Note that all the trails have at least two vertices, and for any two distinct trails \mathcal{E}_i and \mathcal{E}_j , at least one of $A(\mathcal{E}_i, \mathcal{E}_j)$ and $A(\mathcal{E}_j, \mathcal{E}_i)$ is empty. Let D' be the digraph with the set of vertices $\{a_1, \dots, a_t\}$ and the set of arcs $\{(a_i, a_j) | A(\mathcal{E}_i, \mathcal{E}_j) \neq \emptyset \text{ for } 1 \leq i, j \leq t\}$. Note that D' has no 2-circuit. By the fact that D is strong, D' is strong. Let $f : \{a_i, i \in [t]\} \rightarrow \{\mathcal{E}_i, i \in [t]\}$ be a bijective map such that $f(a_i) = \mathcal{E}_i$ for each $i \in [t]$. We has the following claim.

Claim 1. D' has a hamiltonian (directed) circuit.

Proof of Claim 1. Let C be a circuit of D' with the maximum number of vertices. If $V(D') = V(C)$, then C is our desired circuit. So suppose by contradiction that $|V(C)| < t$. Since D' is strong, there exists a dipath Q with only two ends in C and Q has at least three vertices. Let Q be chosen such that the length of the shortest dipath P in C between the endpoints of Q is minimum. Let x, v, y be the first, second, and last vertex of Q (to see Fig.1). Let $P = \langle x, x_1, \dots, y \rangle$ and $Q = \langle x, v, \dots, y \rangle$.

Since C is a circuit with the maximum length, y can not be x_1 nor a vertex x . In deed, if $y = x_1$, then circuit, gotten from C by replacing P with Q , has larger length than that of C which is a contradiction.

If $y = x$, the out-neighbor of x in C is denoted by x_1 . We will show that $(x_1, v) \in A(D')$. In fact, we consider v and x_1 . Since $(x, v), (x, x_1) \in D'$ and D' has no 2-circuits, by Lemma ??, there exist $\varepsilon_1 \in V(f(x)), \varepsilon_2 \in V(f(x_1))$ and $\varepsilon_3 \in V(f(v))$ such that $(\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2), (\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_3) \in A(D)$. By the definition of the locally semicomplete multipartite digraph, either ε_2 and ε_3 belong to the same partite set or there exists an arc between ε_2 and ε_3 in D . If ε_2 and ε_3 belong to the same partite set in D . Since $f(v)$, as a closed trail of D , has at least two vertices and there exists a vertex, say $\varepsilon_4 \in V(f(v))$ such that $(\varepsilon_4, \varepsilon_3) \in A(D)$. By Lemma 2.2(2), $(\varepsilon_4, \varepsilon_2) \in A(D)$ which implies that $(v, x_1) \in A(D')$, then $C_1 := C \cup \{(x, v), (v, x_1)\} - \{(x, x_1)\}$ is the circuit of D' and $|C_1| \geq |C|$ which contradicts the choice of C . Now assume that there exists an arc between

ε_2 and ε_3 in D . If $(\varepsilon_3, \varepsilon_2) \in A(D)$, it implies that $(v, x_1) \in A(D')$ which is a contradiction. So $(\varepsilon_2, \varepsilon_3) \in A(D)$, it implies that $(x_1, v) \in A(D')$.

Fig.1 Circuit C with the dipath Q

By the same reason as considering v and x_1 , then consider v and the out-neighbor, say x_2 , of x_1 in $C \cap D'$. We get that $(x_2, v) \in A(D')$. Repeatedly using this procedures, we can derive that $(t, v) \in A(D')$ for every $t \in V(C)$. Let z be the in-neighbor of x in C . Note that $y = x$. By $(z, v) \in A(D')$, then $C_1 := C \cup Q \cup \{(z, v)\} - \{(z, x), (x, v)\}$ is the circuit of D' with $|C_1| \geq |C|$ which contradicts the choice of C . As a result, y can not equal x_1 nor a vertex x .

Since (x, v) and (x, x_1) are distinct arcs of D' , there exists $t_1, t_2 \in V(f(x))$, $z_1 \in V(f(v))$ and $z_2 \in V(f(x_1))$ such that $(t_1, z_1) \in A(f(x), f(v))$ and $(t_2, z_2) \in A(f(x), f(x_1))$ in D . By Lemma 2.4 and no 2-circuit in D' , $(t_1, z_2) \in A(f(x), f(x_1))$ in D . Since z_1 and z_2 are the out-neighbors of t_1 in D . By Lemma 2.2, either z_1 and z_2 are in the the same partite set or there exists an arc between z_1 and z_2 in D . The later case can not happen. In fact, the arc between z_1 and z_2 in D implies that there exists an arc between v and x_1 in D' . If $(v, x_1) \in D'$, then $C \cup \{(x, v), (v, x_1)\} - \{(x, x_1)\}$ is the circuit with the length longer than that of C , it contradicts with the choice of C . If $(x_1, v) \in D'$, then it contradicts with the shortest dipath P in C . As a result, there exists no arc between v and x_1 in D' . Now assume that z_1 and z_2 are in the same partite set in D , since $f(v)$ contains at least two vertices and $f(v)$ is a closed trail of D , there exists $z_3 \in f(v)$ such that $(z_1, z_3) \in A(f(v)) \subseteq D$, by Lemma 2.2(2), $(z_2, z_3) \in A(D)$, it implies that $(x_1, v) \in A(D')$ which is a contradiction. The proof of Claim is finished.

By Claim 1, D' has a hamiltonian circuit C . Without loss of generality, let $C = a_1 a_2 \cdots a_t a_1$. By Lemma 2.4 and no 2-circuits in D' , there exists $w_i \in \mathcal{E}_i$ for each $i \in [t]$ such that $(v_{i-1}, w_i) \in A(\mathcal{E}_{i-1}, \mathcal{E}_i)$ for each $v_{i-1} \in V(\mathcal{E}_{i-1})$ and $2 \leq i \leq t$, and $(v_t, w_1) \in A(\mathcal{E}_t, \mathcal{E}_1)$ for each $v_t \in V(\mathcal{E}_t)$. As a result, $w_1 w_2 \cdots w_t w_1$ is a circuit of D . Then D is supereulerian with a eulerian digraph $(\bigcup_{i=1}^t \mathcal{E}_i) \cup \{w_1 w_2 \cdots w_t w_1\}$. \square

From Theorem 2.5 and Lemma 2.1, we can derive the following Theorem 2.6.

Theorem 2.6 *Let D be a strong locally semicomplete multipartite digraph. If $\lambda(D) \geq \alpha(D)$, then D is supereulerian.*

Since a semicomplete multipartite digraph is the strong locally semicomplete multipartite digraph, thus the following known result can be gotten directly.

Corollary 2.7([4]) *Let D be a semicomplete multipartite digraph. If $\lambda(D) \geq \alpha(D)$, then D is supereulerian.*

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